

MODIFICATION IPOM - PLASTIC SURGERY IN PATIENTS WITH UMBILICAL HERNIAS**Molchanov M.A.,***Surgeon of the Samara City Hospital № 7, Russia.
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445004, Samara region, Togliatti, Avtozavodskoe highway, 5***Abstract**

In the conditions of modern, constantly progressive medicine, it is a hopeless option to isolate the hernial sac from the subcutaneous tissue to the level of the hernial gate and remove it. This is too traumatic stage of the operation, which is accompanied by detachment of subcutaneous tissue, dissection of aponeurosis, damage to the lymphatic collectors, and bleeding of tissues. When suturing the wound, the synthetic prosthesis remains in contact with subcutaneous tissue, cavities form in the wound, and lymphorrhea persists for a long time. All this requires constant monitoring of the wound and does not exclude the development of complications, the number of which reaches 25%.

Keywords: IPOM plastic surgery, umbilical hernias, prevention of complications.

The aim of our study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the method of intraoperative prevention of wound complications and reducing the trauma of operations in patients with IPOM - plastic surgery in patients with umbilical hernias. During the study period, 82 patients with umbilical hernias were operated on. The size of the defect was from 3 cm² up to 875 cm². There were 37 males and 451 females. The patients age ranges from 18 to 67 years.

Operation technique. Access to the abdominal cavity was performed through an incision in the upper dome of the hernial sac. The implant was fixed along the perimeter of the muscular-aponeurotic contour of the hernial gate from the inside. Through U-shaped sutures were applied with the prosthesis going beyond the edges of the defect by 3-5 cm. With this approach, there is no trauma in the release of the hernial sac, there is no wide detachment of subcutaneous tissue and additional dissections of the aponeurosis. The U-sutures included the omentum tissue, which became a protection against contact injury between the intestine and the prosthesis. Did not allow contact of the reticular prosthesis with subcutaneous tissue. The peritoneal surface of the hernial sac sheets was de-epithelized and stitched over a fixed prosthesis, creating a dense presentation between them. Such techniques significantly reduce the volume of surgical trauma and avoid the accumulation of fluid in the wound.[1]

Operations were performed without isolation of the hernial sac and its removal, which resulted in sig-

nificantly reduces the traumatic nature of interventions. Operations are not accompanied by a wide detachment of subcutaneous tissue, the network of lymphatic collectors remains intact, direct contact of the synthetic prosthesis with subcutaneous tissue is completely excluded, and fluid accumulation in the wound does not occur.[5] Treatment of the hernial sac is atraumatic.

Through the cut the anterior wall of the hernial sac was inserted into the abdominal cavity and all subsequent stages of the operation were performed. The leaves of the hernial sac were separated on clamps and a cavity was created, the work inside of which is convenient, visually controlled and can be carried out with maximum compliance with the conditions of asepsis - there is no overhang of loose fiber, and intestinal loops are easily held in the created cavity and do not fall out on the abdominal wall. From the inside of the hernial sac, it is easier to approach the areas where the soldered organs and the scarring process are most pronounced and are associated with the separation of the intestines from adhesions after possible incomplete infringements in the anamnesis. Preparation for intraperitoneal plastic surgery consisted in freeing the hernial gate from fixed organs and adhesions. There were no additional dissections of the aponeurosis. The condyle-aponeurotic contour of the hernial gate is easily determined by a tight roller on the side of the abdominal cavity.

The prosthesis was fixed using a true muscular-aponeurotic contour of the hernial gate, which is repre-

sented by rectus abdominis muscles in a state of diastasis. The application of U-shaped sutures along the perimeter of the hernial gate with the prosthesis going beyond the edges of the defect at least 3-5 cm excluded the fixation of the implant "edge to edge". The U-sutures also included the omentum tissue, which became a protective pad between the intestinal loops and the prosthesis.[4] Muscle-aponeurotic prosthetic plastic surgery creates conditions that combine the properties of elastic decompression along the suture line due to contractile the ability of the muscles, and high resistance of the aponeurosis to mechanical loads. Creating conditions for damping unloading is extremely important, since it increases the reliability of fixing the prosthesis, reduces postoperative pain and allows patients to be activated early.

Sheets of the preserved hernial sac were sewn over the surface of the prosthesis, the prosthesis was placed between the sheets of the hernial sac from above and the omentum from below, the produced fluid is absorbed by the peritoneum and its accumulation in the wound does not occur.

Special surgical techniques formulated in terms of "peritoneal desquamation" and "peritoneodesis of the hernial sac" have been developed.[2] They were used during surgery as an alternative to removing the hernial sac, and were of particular importance not only in the prevention of wound complications, but also in stimulating reparative processes. During the operation, special physiological properties of the peritoneum were used - traumatization of the mesothelial cover of the peritoneum is accompanied by the release of exudate, which is immediately permeated with fibrin filaments. Formed fibrin adhesions keep the surfaces close together fabrics between each other. Then they form strong connective tissue splices. This mechanism is a protective, physiologically determined property of the peritoneum. It is purposefully used during surgery to improve healing conditions and activate reparative processes.

Mechanical destruction and desquamation of the epithelium (desquamation) of the peritoneal surface of the hernial sac was performed intraoperatively with a special technical device. Destruction of functionally active mesothelial cells suppresses the production of fluid and its accumulation in the wound does not occur. In addition, and most importantly, desquamation creates conditions for the formation of fibrin adhesions and early germination of connective tissue cellular elements (fibroblasts, collagen and elastic fibers). The formulated concept of peritoneodesis of the herniated sac means the creation of a tight connection of its peritoneal parts. surfaces with fabrics. The herniated sac sheets were stitched over the implant in such a way that their de-epithelized peritoneal surfaces fit snugly to the surface of the fixed implant. Between the connected surfaces, active germination of connective tissue elements occurs, which freely penetrate through the implant cells and, fusing with it, create strong adhesions with the formation of the so-called "prosthetic aponeurosis". The use of "desquamation" and "peritoneodesis" of the hernial sac creates special, most favorable conditions for

the course of reparative processes and is the most effective treatment for the patient. a preventive measure for the development of complications.[7]

The use of intraperitoneal plastic surgery makes it possible to perform operations from smaller incisions. When choosing access, the incision length was determined by the size of the hernial gate and in accordance with them. Surgery through the hernial sac cavity creates quite comfortable conditions for performing intraperitoneal plastic surgery from an incision corresponding to the size of the hernial gate. Such calculations significantly reduced the size of the section. In particular, they used variable access. It was used in patients with large hernial defects and minor soft tissue excesses that do not require extensive excision. Two small incisions were made, from which the entire volume of the intervention was performed. A certain area of the hernial gate was opened through one of the incisions and U-shaped sutures were applied to the implant from the abdominal side. The implant was inserted through one incision, then the prosthesis was moved inside the abdominal cavity and fixed through the aperture of another incision. Soft tissue dislocation allows tunneling of the implant and its gradual fixation under visual control. Removal of excess soft tissues in patients with large hernias was performed according to pre-planned reference lines. It is important that the fabrics after excision can be sewn without tension. To get more accurate landmarks, it is advisable to use the middle line of the abdomen, applied from the xiphoid process to the womb. The hernial sac was shifted laterally without significant tension and a line was drawn on the skin at the base of the hernial sac coinciding with the midline of the abdominal wall. Then, the hernial sac was shifted in the opposite direction and the middle line on the skin of the removed hernial sac was also marked. When excising tissues along these lines, the opposite edges of the wound correspond to the middle line and are located in a state of adequate matching and tension.[3]

The distance between the middle and posteroaxillary lines on each side was measured. From the posterior-axillary line, a centimeter tape was placed, going to the side of the laterally removed hernial sac and making marks on the skin. The marks correspond to the midline of the abdomen. The same marks were made on the hernial sac, which was taken in the opposite direction. After excision along these reference lines, the edges of the wound coincide with the middle line and do not experience tension during stitching.

This approach simplifies the selection of the cut line and direction. For hernial gates that are wider than their length, cross-sections are recommended. As the wound heals, such incisions do not acquire an aesthetic appearance. In cosmetic terms, median incisions look more preferable. When working from the inside of the hernial sac, there is no such dependence, since there is no need to isolate the hernial sac, and its cavity provides quite adequate conditions for fixing the implant in any form of hernial gate. The use of median access becomes a working standard and method of choice. Cross sections no access rights were used. Figural incisions were

used in cases where significant excess adipose skin tissue was removed.

Conclusions. Wound healing took place by primary tension. No significant tissue edema was observed. Wound complications were noted in 3 patients. There were no intra-abdominal complications. There were no relapses during follow-up of patients for up to 6 months. Patients are active and functional. The intraperitoneal approach to umbilical hernia repair expands intraoperative opportunities for the prevention of wound complications.

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